

ASSESSMENT OF THE CONTRIBUTION OF *PARKIA BIGLOBOSA* (JACQ.) BENTH TO RURAL LIVELIHOOD IN OYO STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Upsurge in population has resulted in pressure on many tree species out of which *Parkia biglobosa* is not left out. The species is highly valued for its socio economic potentials. The study therefore assessed the contribution of *P. biglobosa* to rural livelihood in Oyo State, Nigeria. This is to generate information on the socio-economic values of the species to the rural communities. Structured questionnaire were used for data collection. Stratified sampling technique was used to divide the study area into three based on ecological zones where twenty percent of each ecological zone was selected. A multistage sampling procedure was used in collecting data on socio-economic importance. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, cross tabulation and chi-square. The result of chi-square analysis revealed that degree of contributions of the species to daily income of processors, marketers and harvesters in dry woodland and moist woodland were significant ($P < 0.05$) but not significant in rainforest ecological zones. Also, the chi-square test for relationship between degrees of contribution of *P. biglobosa* to household consumption was significant in the study area. It is recommended that domestication and plantation establishment of the species should be encouraged by the forestry stakeholders in order to improve the contribution of the species to the rural household livelihoods and meet the high demand for the products of the species.

KEYWORDS: *Parkia biglobosa*, Livelihood, Socio-economics, rural communities.

INTRODUCTION

Traditional farming systems in the tropics have been known to rely on trees and shrubs for soil fertility maintenance and regeneration (FAO, 2004). Trees play a vital role in this process and leguminous trees have added advantages over other trees in this respect. Judicious use-of multipurpose trees in the farming system aids in the recycling of nutrients and water from deeper soil horizons, nitrogen fixation, soil thermo and water regulations and prevention of leaching and run-off (FAO, 2004).

Multipurpose trees also provide shade for animals and crops, provide animal fodder and in most cases supply human food. In the farming system, these trees are capable of enhancing both crop productions, through soil fertility maintenance and livestock production through increased availability of high quality feeds. The efficiency of this, however, depends on the species used and the manner of their integration and management within the cropping system (Bayala, 2006).

Farmers have long recognized the importance of trees. They deliberately incorporate trees in production systems (Sène, 1985 and Hopkins, 1985). Inquiry into current and past farming practices has clearly shown that rural people have a wealth of knowledge as to which trees make agricultural crops grow more successfully, which provide fodder during dry seasons, and which help to hold soils for more successful farming on sloping land (Bayala, 2006).

Majority of the rural households depends on forest resources to meet subsistence need for staple and supplementary foods, construction materials, fuel, medicine, cash, local ecosystem services and farm inputs, such as animal feed and nutrients for crops (Raintree, 1999). In rural areas, the contribution of multipurpose indigenous agroforestry fruit trees such as *Parkia biglobosa* to food supply is essential for food security as they help to bridge 'hunger period' when stored food supplies are dwindling and the harvest is not yet available.

Traditionally, farmers in Africa preserve these valuable resources by nurturing them in agricultural lands in the agroforestry system, characterised by scattered trees on fallow and cultivated land. The system has worked well in the past, but it is now loosing its vitality under increasing population pressure (Boffa, 1999). In fallow, the incidence of protected trees of varied species and sizes indicates a strong correlation between conservation and the productive values of a given species (Bonkougou, 2002).

The natural forest can no longer sustain the demand on it for timber, food and other forms of livelihood. This has resulted in attention being shifted to indiscriminate exploitation of many tree crops in free areas including *Parkia biglobosa* regardless of its numerous socio-economic and ecological values (Ismaila and Abibou, 2002).

It is also known that, in traditional farming, certain tree species are often left by farmers either as source of wood for building, fruits, medicinal purposes, yam stakes and shade plants, among others. In spite of the fact that these multipurpose tree species is found on farmlands, their potentials in agroforestry are not fully documented (Popoola and Tee, 2001). It is therefore necessary to study socio-economic potentials of the species to rural livelihood in order to provide necessary information for the planning of conservation and sustainable management of the species.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study area is Oyo State. It is located in South Western part of Nigeria. It lies between latitudes 7⁰N and 9⁰N and between longitudes 2.5⁰E and 5⁰E. It has a total land area of 28,454 square kilometres. The vegetation pattern of the State is that of rain forest in the South and guinea savannah to the North. Thick forest in the South gives way to grassland interspersed with trees in the North (www.oyostate.gov.ng).

A multistage sampling procedure was used to collect data on socio-economic importance of *Parkia biglobosa*. In the first stage of sampling, the three ecological zones of Oyo state i.e. Dry-woodland, moist-woodland and Rainforest were purposively selected for the study. As second stage of sampling, two Local Government Areas from each ecological zone were randomly selected to make a total of 6 Local Government Areas.

Purposive sampling technique was used to select four (4) villages/communities located in four cardinal points of each Local Government Area (North, South, East and West) so as to cover sociocultural features of the study areas. In each community, quota sampling was used to sample 5 farmers, 5 harvesters, 5 processors and 5 marketers giving a total of 480 respondents for the 24 communities. Focus Group discussion and target informant interview were also employed in the data collection process. This was to obtain additional and sensitive information which people may not want to give willinly in questionnaire survey.

Descriptive and cross tabulation were used in analyzing the data and these include: percentages, frequency distribution and chi-square.

Hypothesis tested

Ho: There is no association between contributions of the species to households' livelihood and ecological zones.

The Chi-square test is given by:

$$X^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i},$$

Where

X^2 = Chi- square

O_i = Contribution of the species to households' income

E_i = Expected frequencies

n = the number of cells in the table.

Fig. 1 Map of Oyo State Showing Study Locations

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic information on the marketers of *P. biglobosa*

Gender distribution of respondents

In the three ecological zones, marketers of *P. biglobosa* products were all females. The domination of the marketers of the species by female may be an indication that marketing of the products of these species like many other Non-timber forest products are regarded as feminine business. This agrees with the report of Popoola (1999) and Ogunwande *et.al* (2009) that women play crucial role in agroforestry enterprise development at all stages which include marketing.

Age distribution of respondents

In the study area, 21.1% of the marketers of *P. biglobosa* respondents were within age 20-30 years, 42.2% were of age 31-40 years, and 38.9% at age 41-50. Those above 51 years were 8.9% (Fig. 2). This indicates that population of marketers had a relatively young and active people. This is in agreement with Jimoh and Adedokun (2005) that *P. Biglobosa* production and marketing is an energy-demanding task requiring physical strength which only active people are able to exert. The involvement of young people in the business indicates the posterity of the business. This is an omen for sustainable management of the species. Since the younger generation who benefit from the business will contribute to its conservation.

Marital status of respondent

The majority of the marketers were married (Fig.3). This indicates that the business is profitable to certain extent for people to depend on it for a living in their families especially women, widowed and divorcee who depend on the income to support their homes. Therefore for continue support of the species to the welfare of the families, sustainable management of the species must be ensured.

Educational Status of respondents

50% of the marketers of *P. biglobosa* respondents had no formal education. Those with primary education constitute 45.6% and Secondary education had 5.6%. (Fig. 4). Halve of the respondents had no formal

education as educational background may not have influence in the marketing of the product, but it has its importance in business for effective transaction and proper record keeping (Ogunwande *et. al*, 2009).

Fig. 2: Pie-chart showing age distribution of the marketers of *P. biglobosa* products in the three ecological zones of Oyo State.

Fig. 3: Pie-chart showing marital status of the marketers of *P. biglobosa* products in the three ecological zones of Oyo State.

Fig. 4: Pie-chart showing education status of the marketers of *P. biglobosa* products in the three ecological zones of Oyo State.

Socio economic information on the marketers of *P. biglobosa*

Annual income from the sales

From the sales of *P. biglobosa*, 93.7% of the respondents realized average of ₦ 72,000 per annum. This amounts to about 50% of annual income of the respondents (Fig. 5). Majority of the marketers of the species process the product by themselves, the involvement of which might be due to high level of demand of the product. At the same time, the respondents engage in other occupations like trading and farming. From marketing of the product, an average income of ₦72,000 is realized annually. The fact that 50% of income comes from the marketing of *P. biglobosa* products indicates the level of support of the species to the rural livelihood.

The chi square test shows that the degree of contribution of *P. biglobosa* to marketer’s annual income in dry woodland and moist woodland is significant at 5% level of probability but not significant in the rain forest (Table 1). This might be as a result of low abundance of the species in the ecological zone. Though the daily income level is the same as income from other businesses in the study area, the income from the marketing of the species serve as a lifeline for those engaged in the business. This agrees with assertion of FAO (1995) that many forest based businesses provide substantial employment opportunity and supplementary income.

Fig. 5: Bar-chart showing annual income from the sales of *P. biglobosa* products in the three ecological zones of Oyo State.

Socio-Economic Information on the Processors of *P. biglobosa*

The species generates 20% of the processor's annual employment. This is probably because seeds of *P. biglobosa* are much more abundant and that demand for its products is higher. Involvement of majority in the processing of *P. biglobosa* corroborates the finding of Oyerinde and Daramola (2004) that higher percentage of the population of rural dwellers is directly involved in the processing of many non- timber forest products.

All year round employment and income is being generated from processing of *P. biglobosa*, it contribute 50% to annual income of the processors in the study area. This finding agrees with FAO (1995) that forest based activities provide supplementary sources of family income apart from agriculture.

The chi-square test indicates that the degree of contribution of *P. biglobosa* to processors annual income in dry woodland and moist woodland are significant at 5% level of probability but not significant in the rainforest (Table 2). The significant contribution of the species in dry woodland and moist woodland conforms to the findings of Bayala *et.al*, (2005) that rural households derive sustenance livelihoods from NTFPs.

Socio-Economic Information on the Harvesters of *P. biglobosa*

Harvesting of *P. biglobosa* is carried out through out the harvesting season. As a result of this, conservation of the species is crucial for sustainability of socio-economic values. Harvesters engaged in harvesting for 2 – 3 months annually. This implies that supplementary employments are being generated (25% of annual employment) during the harvesting season of this species in addition to their primary occupation. In the same vein, harvesting of *P. biglobosa* accounts for 38% of harvesters annual income.

The chi square test shows that the degree of contribution of *P. biglobosa* to harvesters' daily income in dry woodland and moist woodland is significant at 5% level of probability (Table 3). This shows that income realized here plays crucial role in household financial as such funds come handy during emergency cash needs (Hopskins, 1990).

Consumption of *P. biglobosa* in Local Diets

Almost every respondent consume *P. biglobosa* everyday. About 35% of daily food intake contains *P. biglobosa* (Table 4). This shows the important contribution of the species to food security and confirms the finding of Jimoh and Adedokun (2005) that those who consume *iru* daily have the largest percentage (64.7%). It is therefore expedient to ensure sustainability of this species through effective management.

The chi square test shows that the degree of contribution of *P. biglobosa* to household consumption in dry woodland moist woodland and rainforest is significant at 5% level of probability (Table 5). Therefore, the consumption of the products has become part and parcel of traditional dishes and does not depend upon the seasonality of the fruits. It is thus obvious that the product contributes to household food security in the area. This however necessitated proper management of the species for sustainability.

Table 1: Chi-square Test for Association between the Degree of Contribution of *P. biglobosa* to Marketers' Annual Income and Ecological zones.

Species	Ecological zones	X ²	Tab. X ²	Df
<i>P. biglobosa</i>	Dry woodland	14.40*	11.67	4
	Moist woodland	12.9*	11.67	4
	Rainforest	11.54ns	11.67	4

* = Significant at 5% level of probability. ns = Not significant at 5% level of probability.

Table 2: Chi-square Test for Association between the Degree of Contribution of *P. biglobosa* to Processors' Annual Income and Ecological zones.

Species	Ecological zones	X ²	Tab. X ²	Df
<i>P. biglobosa</i>	Dry woodland	14.87*	11.67	4
	Moist woodland	12.83*	11.67	4
	Rainforest	11.61ns	11.67	4

* = Significant at 5% level of probability. ns = Not significant at 5% level of probability.

Table 3: Association between the Degree of Contribution of *P.biglobosa* to Harvesters' Annual Income and Ecological zones.

Species	Ecological zones	X ²	Tab. X ²	Df
<i>P.biglobosa</i>	Dry woodland	30.20*	11.67	4
	Moist woodland	33.80*	11.67	4
	Rainforest	5.40ns	11.67	4

* = Significant at 5% level of probability. ns = Not significant at 5% level of probability.

Table 4: Consumption of *P. biglobosa* in the three ecological zones of Oyo State.

	Total	
	Freq.	%
Consumption of <i>P. biglobosa</i>		
Yes	117	97.5
No	3	2.5
Total	120	100
Frequency of consumptions		
Every day	109	90.8
Once in 2 days	11	9.2
Once in 3 days	0	0
Once in a week	0	0
Total	120	100
Number of times daily		
Once a day	68	56.7
Twice a day	45	37.5
3 times a day	0	0
No response	7	5.8
Total	120	100

Source: Field survey, 2011

Table 5: Association between the Degree of Contribution of *P.biglobosa* to Household Consumption and Ecological zones.

Species	Ecological zones	X ²	Tab. X ²	Df
<i>P.biglobosa</i>	Dry woodland	32.40*	11.67	4
	Moist woodland	38.12*	11.67	4
	Rainforest	36.10*	11.67	4

* = Significant at 5% level of probability.

CONCLUSION

Harvesting, processing and marketing of *P. biglobosa* play a significant role in food security, employment and income generation. The degree of contribution of *P. biglobosa* to food security, income generation and employment in the three ecological zones were significant at 5% level of probability. It was observed that socio-economic importance of the species can not be over-emphasized and therefore their management should be intensified. In the same vein, enrichment planting and domestication of the two species should be encouraged by the forestry stakeholders in order to meet high demand for the products of the species. More so, farmers should be encouraged by forestry stake holders to improve on the retention and planting of new trees for the increase in the socio-economic values which they are deriving from the species.

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Received for Publication: 10/02/12

Accepted for Publication: 20/04/12

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